

Modern Vietnamese fables

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****Editorial note:*** This short piece reproduces Prof Nancy K. Napier's book review posted on Amazon.com [1]. The references are added for clarity.

Top review from the United States

Nancy K. Napier, Author

★★★★★ Verified Purchase

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Reviewed in the United States 🇺🇸 on February 16, 2023

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Quan-Hoang Vuong's book, The Kingfisher Story Collection, joins this long running genre, and offers a Vietnamese slant. Vuong's main character in a series of twenty-one short stories, what Vuong calls "snippets," is a bird. The sage Kingfisher lives in a village of birds and other animals and over time, helps his colleagues learn lessons about society, relationships, pride, decency, and more. The stories are short, snappy, and feel like fables of old, with their lessons and humor. As with other fables, Kingfisher

Figure. The review on Amazon: <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

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Quan-Hoang Vuong's book, [The Kingfisher Story Collection](#) [1], joins this long-running genre and offers a Vietnamese slant. Vuong's main character in a series of twenty-one short stories, what Vuong calls "snippets," is a bird. The sage Kingfisher lives in a village of birds and other animals and, over time, helps his colleagues learn lessons about society, relationships, pride, decency, and more. The stories are short, snappy, and feel like fables of old, with their lessons and humor. As with other fables, Kingfisher exemplifies the sage village elder (or near elder) who stops and thinks and offers the best responses he can to challenges, problems, and deep questions.

I've spent years working in Vietnam and trying to understand the [people and culture](#). This book, which I read when I returned home from a trip to Hanoi, made me a little homesick for Vietnam. It is a lively read and offers a charming peek into Vietnamese culture, delightful for a person who knows a lot—or nothing—about Vietnam.

References

[1] Napier NK. (2023). Modern Vietnamese fables. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R2XP0UTUJ4GX23/>

[2] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

